

Performance Analysis of Modern Management-Based Village Officials in Bube Village, Suwawa District, Bone Bolango Regency

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Abstract

This study aims to describe the performance of village officials who apply the principles of office management to achieve the goals of effective governance, where previously there was a lack of training provided to Village Officials regarding the use of modern-based applications such as the application of the Village Financial System (Siskeudes), and the Village Asset Management System (Sipades) and lack of office facilities that support performance in meeting work needs.

This research method uses a descriptive type with a qualitative approach, through the interview, observation, and documentation techniques. As informants in this study are the Village Head, Village Secretary, Head of Village Financial Affairs, and Head of General Planning and Administrative Affairs.

The results showed that: 1) Assessment of the performance of village officials containing modern management principles, namely discipline the performance appraisal of an employee in the Bube villages, discipline has not gone well, some of the village apparatuses that rarely enter, 2) the application of modern management in the management of the administration system in the Bube village government, has been implemented and at the end of each month a meeting is held for performance evaluation even though in reality some village officials do not carry out their duties and responsibilities optimally, 3) There has been no in-depth training on the Sipades application due to the lack of budget for training for the village asset processing system in 2020.

Keywords: Performance of Village Officials, and Modern Management

1. Introduction

Village Officers are employees of the lowest level of government administration who have obligations and responsibilities to provide services to residents, and assist the Village

Head in carrying out his duties to distribute services in accordance with the wishes of residents, therefore Village Officers are required to have commitment, expertise, skills and feelings of sincere attention and want great empathy in carrying out their duties to serve residents. It is hoped that residents will feel secure and satisfied with the services of Village Officers in resolving all administrative cases in the Village.

In the application of a development in this post-renewal period, the government has intended to increase the effectiveness and efficiency and productivity of its apparatus as well as mandated by the outline of the national development program, if our Government system adheres to the principles of decentralization, deconcentration, and medebewind, as a result of the position of Government as an instrument of state administration in carrying out the allocation, regulation, and stabilization of the national energy base can be carried out to the lowest level of government.

The government has a pioneering identity in implementing development programs, as a result, it requires public administration that can carry out government tasks and development tasks.

In creating the mandate, the application of Modern Management is necessary as a stage of utilization of the state apparatus. The main root that does not change is that the Village Government as the executor of the Government at the Village level with the attached authority is also currently regulated by government regulations. Many aspects can affect the capacity of the Village apparatus to perform their duties, for example, the lack of a base of data access and communication such as the current situation where the Village apparatus does not receive technical education, training nurseries, or careful data related to the management of Government administration, most notably in using applications that are modern technology platforms.

The results of the monitoring that was attempted, researchers saw that some Village Officers felt difficulties in handling the profession, this management was due to the lack of nursery training accompanied by Village Officers and the lack of adequate office facilities. Not only that, sluggish services, for example, in the administration of message records such as for the needs of E-ID cards, birth certificates, and others, are far from perfect, technological capabilities, lack of insight caused by the lack of data, nursery training or technical education accompanied by Village Officers Bube can cause the management to be intertwined. Data disclosure in an open way of industrial affairs is very meaningful for the kurusanayak industry. This management is attempted as a form of clarity and accountability of industry management to stakeholders.

The continuity of data from the industry can be used as estimation material for stakeholders in the collection of decisions. The application and management of good corporate governance better known as good corporate governance is a plan that emphasizes the meaning of the rights of shareholders to get data correctly, carefully, and at the right time. Not only that, GCG also proves the role of the industry to say (disclosure) all data on the financial and non-financial capabilities of the industry in a careful, timely, and transparent manner. Therefore, both public and private industries must view good corporate governance (GCG) not as an accessory, but as an effort to increase the industry's capabilities and numbers. Going from that view, when dealing with the situation in the research position that the researchers tried, precisely in Bube Village, Suwawa Subdistrict, Bone Bolango Regency, it is

not yet categorized as advanced, the village officials are not well versed in the regulations from the upper levels and the operating system of applications with modern technology platforms, as a result, the Government activities are not running optimally. Based on the researcher's early observations, it is evident that the base of people's energy and the ability of the Bube Village apparatus in managing the administration of the village government is not yet maximum, as a result an in-depth observation is needed to recognize the position of Village Officers in carrying out the Government system in the village which is based on industrial functions and practices the principles of Good Corporate Governance.

Particularly in creating good governance rules and supporting national development in the maximum way is the availability of a base of energy of professional people and modern technological office facilities. An office must have a variety of various overall activity facilities such as office buildings, PCs, desks, benches cabinets, and other supporting facilities such as bureau transportation. Activity facilities are a form of service to employees in supporting abilities. Periset concludes that the availability of a base of people energy and activity facilities has an important impact on the capacity of Village Officers in Bube Village, Suwawa Sub-district, Bone Bolango Regency.

Analysis

The analysis comes from the English word analysis which means: to peel, describe, discuss, and review. Analysis is a way of breaking down something into separate factors to understand the character, relationship, and contribution of each factor. In linguistics, analysis or analysis is an observation carried out on a language to research the structure of the language in an in-depth way. For KBBI, analysis is the tracking of an incident (essay, action, and the like) to recognize the real conditions (causes, reasons, reasons, etc.); the decomposition of something into its various parts, and the study of the parts themselves and the bonds between the parts to get the right interpretation and description of the meaning of the totality; (Management).

Performance

The interpretation of Ability is the result obtained by an agency that is profit-oriented and non-profit-oriented that is produced throughout duration. Ability is the result of the interaction or functioning of the elements of motivation, expertise, and assumption in a person. Ability is about what a person does and wants to bring about a result. Ability is the result of activities by way of quality and amount obtained by an employee in performing his duties following the responsibilities distributed to him. Ability is the production power resulting from the number of objects and services produced with the amount of activity power, capital, and energy base utilized in the creation.

Village Apparatus

The Village Apparatus is one of the tools of the Village government, not only the Village Head. According to the conclusion of Article 1 point 3 of the Village Law, the role of the Village Officer is to 'assist' the Village Head in carrying out the functions of the Government. The Village Apparatus or Officer is regulated in Articles 48 to 53 of the Village

Law. In a nutshell, these articles organize the roles and obligations of Village Officers; promotion and dismissal; income; and prohibitions in carrying out obligations.

Financial Management

Financial Management is a part of the industry's directive obligations with important responsibilities in the form of significant decisions regarding the capitalization and financing of the industry. [When connected with the principle of management, the acquisition, and use of the budget in the sense that it must be carried out efficiently and efficiently. Financial management is the entire activity of bonding with some goals. Therefore, the decision-making purpose of the financial administrator can be divided into 3 zones, namely decisions with capital, funding, and assets."

Operations Management

Based on the book Operation Management Operation is part of a business field agency that works to produce objects or services. Objects are physical equipment that includes anomalous materials. parts, subassemblies such as motherboards that are part of a PC, as well as final products such as a telephone head. On the other hand, a service is an activity that shares a numerical mix of duration, position, and intellectual numbers. On the other hand, surgical management is a system or method of management that produces objects or distributes services.

Modern Management

Modern management is management that in its period is characterized by having studied management as a science that has the basics of objective common sense, as a result of which many associate management experts or economists to carry out research on management which creates various philosophies or management movements. These theories were initially pioneered by Robert Owen, Adam Smith, Charles Babbage and Max Weber. Next are the claims that describe this type of management, namely: management cannot be viewed as a technical method with a fast way; management must be systematic, and the approach used must be with careful estimation; the body as a totality and the approach of individual administrators to supervision must be with atmosphere; an encouragement approach that creates employee commitment to the goals of the body is needed. Modern terminology, in The Contemporary English- Indonesia, is expressed most recently; modernism: modern actions, thoughts, popular actions; renewal: renewal to fit the current era. Modern interpretation proves that there is an exchange of something that was previously an approved method of doing something. Modern management is management based on a number of perspectives, such as: system design, analysis of provisions, the meaning of people and the social responsibility of people in the organization. Modern management is also being constantly derived from the best views of management. Modern management is formed based on the best practices of management, which are assisted by the latest approaches, guidance, methods and actions.

Definition of Management

Management is a special way consisting of actions of planning, organizing, mobilizing, and regulating to ensure and achieve goals through the exploitation of the energy base of people and other energy bases."

Definition of Human Resource Management

Management of the energy base of people is something planning, organizing, coordinating, implementing, and supervising the logistics, development, provision of responding services, integrating, and dividing resource activities in the chart of achieving agency goals.

Definition of discipline

Kedispilinan is a tool that a superior uses to talk to his subordinates so that they want to change an attitude as an effort to increase the understanding and willingness of a person to obey all industry regulations and legal question norms. From that interpretation, it can be concluded that an activity order is an action of sold actions and actions that are following the rules, whether written or not recorded, and violations will have consequences for violations.

Definition of Modern Management

Modern management is management based on how much management is based on how much view, sort, system design, analysis of provisions. This means that the aspects of people and social responsibility of people in modern management bodies are also being constantly derived from the best views and management of modern management is built based on the best practices of management which are helped by the latest guidance approaches, methods, and actions.

Principles of Modern Management

- 1) Management cannot be looked at as a method in a tight way (share, method, and principle).
- 2) Management must be systematic and the approach used must be carefully estimated.
- 3) The agency as a totality and the individual administrator's approach to supervision must match the situation.

A motivational approach that creates employee commitment to agency goals is essential—benefits of modern management on village governance. Modern management will not be of much use if it is not assisted by elements that have influenced its success in its implementation. In many cases, the successful implementation of Modern Management success will be greatly influenced by various factors, including the Energy Base of People, infrastructure, and Data Systems. In connection with that, continuing to be a modern office continues to be a lot of data that can be accessed, and continues to be a great opportunity that can be used for the needs of the agency or institution. Modern offices today continue to approach the atmosphere and lead to a time when the use of paper is decreasing. Something in the future may be large office correspondence no longer using paper "paperless). Data alteration in its various forms will be carried out via email "electric post" using the internet, BBM, e-mail, and the web, as a result of which the data that is creamed and obtained more quickly, with the cost continuing to be economical.

Village Financial Management

Financial management is a form of administrative activity that is carried out in the form of some steps that include planning, storage of usage, recording, and supervision after which the way the budget goes in an agency. For the regulation of the Minister of Home Affairs (Permendagri) No. 113 of 2014 concerning Village financial management, it is stated

that Village financial management is defined as the totality of activities that include planning, implementation, administration, and accountability of village finances.

Village Asset Management

Law No. 6/2014 on Villages, Article 77 paragraph (1) states that the management of Village-owned assets is undertaken to improve the safety and livelihoods of villagers and to improve the safety and livelihoods of villagers and increase Village revenues. The purpose of managing Village-owned assets is in line with the previous regulation stipulated in Permendagri No.4/2007 in which the Village Administration used all of it for the needs and services of the Village residents.

2. Methods

This research method uses a descriptive type with a qualitative approach, through the interview, observation, and documentation techniques. As informants in this study are the Village Head, Village Secretary, Head of Village Financial Affairs, and Head of General Planning and Administrative Affairs.

3. Results

Work result

The handling of obligations attempted by Bube Village features is a form of obligation that must be completed and must be for all Bube Village officers because, with the handling of obligations, it can be seen that the extent of the level of dedication and can share something good and relieving services for the village community. Not only that but there are many more that are related to each handling of obligations from the leader, such as the superior of the Village government is the Village head and if there are obligations that must be completed by the government above it, it can be from the sub-district government and others. Handling the profession with good and appropriate duration is a measure of success in achieving the profession in the dimensions of expertise, accuracy, and responsibility.

Each employee if there is a profession that is always delayed until the application and handling will cause other professions to be neglected. From the results of questions and answers and observations attempted by researchers to the way obligations are handled by some Bube Village officials is less efficient and efficient. The Village Secretary stated that the handling of obligations from the Village apparatus is not good, such as a lack of energy base of people from the Village apparatus so aspects of expertise in handling obligations. The insight of office administration is one of the views that are very meaningful in distributing services, and administrative progress that results in a necessity regarding the increase in insight and abilities by the actors, namely Village government officials in the management of completing the tasks available, whether it is related to services to local villagers or the government above, The knowledge and skills of Village officials are also caused by the lack of office facilities, which results in the completion of obligations at the Bube Village office being a little slow, the availability of data technology and communication platform tools at the Bube Village office, such as PCs, is not yet in its totality and has not met the analogy with

the number of Village officials available, as a result making its use obligatory to take turns with other officers.

Discipline

Discipline related to the level of discipline possessed by officers includes discipline to the application of any provisions or orders from the leadership mean orders that arrive from a larger government can be from the sub-district office and can also be from the leader is the village head. Actions and obedient attitudes that concern the accuracy of duration in a profession can also be listed among others in the management of carrying out tasks in serving citizens and can also be other obligations, for example from the leadership, discipline in the results of this research is order with the duration of attendance and return of officers from the Bube Village office. Duration is a discipline that greatly influences the ability and action which in turn has a good influence on the effectiveness or efficiency of the results of the activities of the Bube Village officers, not only that, order requires a very large understanding as a result of being able to help in the management of achieving the ability and action and helping in the management of achieving something that is the goal of the body and maximum. The discipline that affects is the discipline of duration and professional discipline and action where both must be able to be in line and harmony if you want to get good results and greatly affect the results to be obtained. Observations and questions and answers carried out by researchers to officers at the Bube Village office, in reviewing from the discipline marker that the orderliness of Village officials to the duration of activities is very poor, including some Village officials who are not often attending activities. The reality that researchers have in the field, that the Village apparatus is in shifts by the Village apparatus, the number of Village apparatus there are 8 people including the Village Head, Village Secretary, Village Head, Village Government Section head of planning, Kasie Kesra, and Village Financial Section head.

Leadership

Leadership is often associated with the position or attitude of a person who can influence and focus others to achieve maximum results from specific goals. The success of a superior Village head is measured by the results achieved and the fulfillment of the goals of the vision and objectives formalized in the Village RPJM deed for 6 years or during the era of the position of the elected Village head, and to achieve the success of that goal, the Village head must play a clear role in focusing his apparatus in carrying out and completing the obligations and responsibilities of each. The results of monitoring and questioning in this research prove that in the application of his duties, the head of Bube Village practices modern management principles to the rules of governance in Bube Village, such as; deciding on the activity of assessing the ability of the Village officers at least once a month to measure and calculate the expertise of his officers in completing their obligations and responsibilities, and practicing obedience to duration and attitude.

Ability

In principle, the application of modern management to the base of people's energy (HRM) is assisted by the clarity of the participating parts or bodies (listed citizens) and the conclusion of the limits of authority, roles, and responsibilities of each part in a real and strong

way. Therefore, modern management cannot be observed as a purely technical method—reliable needs to have technical advantages and be able to cooperate with other bodies. Therefore, if they have good actions, insights, and skills, they can be said to be reliable. In modern management applications, all energy-based people have a great activity ethic, logical actions, analytical and analytical assumptions, respect for duration, cooperation, proactivity, and data figures.

Good insight, insight into the technical tasks to be acquired, as well as leadership skills, must also have technical and administrative skills or expertise, listed management skills, allocation of energy bases, appropriate control, and the use of warm interpersonal ties, without neglecting the goal of achieving the management objectives of the Village Government. A local government body requires the existence of apparatus or local features that have expertise in ties with the profession as a result of creating a maximum. Based on the opinion above, activity expertise is the capacity of people to perform various obligations in a special profession. Based on the monitoring in the square of each Village officer in charge of the Village Government, it has been better than last year, but the expertise of bube Village officers does not mean anything for a profession, if it is not supported by a sense of responsibility and expertise in completing its duties is an illustration that currently the bube Village office lacks facilities in the form of a pc, printer, activity table, and a small activity room.

Employee Discipline

Order is a significant management in people's life factors, and obedience has a relationship with self-regulation (Self-control) which is part of the person's obedience is a condition created using a series of attitudes describing the number of obedience to a provision. By the previous review, it can be concluded that the discipline of employees and the responsibility of Village officials in the implementation of their obligations and uses are lacking, starting from the effectiveness of office hours which should be 07:30 to 16: 00 but in fact on activity days sometimes it is not open and sometimes it is not until 4 pm has closed, want to but if there is a profession pressing Village officers without being obliged to force them to be on duty late into the night especially entering activities on Saturdays and Sundays, but for some Village officers it is very far from being obedient especially responsible with their obligations and functions.

Cooperation

As explained earlier, it can be concluded that cooperation is the willingness to work together with others in a way that is totality and becomes part of a group in dismantling a case, it can also be interpreted those similar activities are activities carried out by each body and have positions and responsibilities that are similar in size and are all tasked with achieving one goal. Observations and questions and answers carried out by researchers to officers at the Bube Village office in reviewing similar activities, if each Village officer has a profession that differs from one another, and is always available to help as long as there is a duration in completing the obligation even though it is not his obligation but helps the power and mind to complete the obligation but, when the officer responsible for the profession is not

located in the office for the duration let alone absent from activities as a result this management greatly affects the way the profession is handled.

4. Discussion

Work Result

Based on the results of interviews with 4 research informants, it can be seen that the results of the work of village officials through the performance assessment of the Bube village apparatus are reported at the end of each month.

According to Mr. AH's statement regarding the work of the village apparatus, namely;

"In managing the administration of the village apparatus, especially the head of affairs (Kaur) and the head of the Section (Kasie) using the application to facilitate the completion of administrative reports, both financial reports, village assets or population, and at the end of each month I as the leader in this office, hold a coordination meeting related to evaluating the performance and work results of my apparatus, and in fact some village officials do not carry out their duties and responsibilities so that as a leader I have to act decisively several times so that the management and completion of the administration is even better."

The next resource person, Mrs. MB, as the village secretary, stated the results of the performance of the village apparatus, namely:

"The village apparatus consists of 8 (eight) people, including the Village Head, Village Secretary, Village Head 1, Village Head 2, Village Government Section, Planning Section, Welfare Section, and Village Financial Section. The ability of the Bube Village Government is lacking, among others, regarding the orderliness of the Village apparatus, some of the Village apparatus that do not often enter activities can be observed from activities in the Village office can be counted how many people show up, often some do not show up at the Village office not only orderliness, such as the handling of obligations is not good, such as the obligation to collect Village profile data that has not been worked on until now".

According to the statement of the Head of Finance

"DK (financial head) the results of the activities of the Village officers the lack of upgrading of the nursery shared by the Village officers related to the use of applications related to the Village financial system and the village legacy management system in the implementation of the siskeudes and sipades applications still often occur trouble and error systems that often make the apparatus have to be extra careful not to mention the limited knowledge and understanding of the bube village apparatus in operating the application in addition they also have not received training or technical guidance on procedures or techniques in managing finances and assets. still not optimal, this affair is influenced by the limited knowledge and understanding of the bube village apparatus in operating the application. "It is still not optimal, this matter is influenced by the lack of knowledge in carrying out each tupoksi and overlapping jobs, such as work that should be done by the Head of Welfare is done by the Head of Government so that their work is neglected, as well as the lack of a sense of responsibility from each of our village officials."

In contrast, Mrs. NB (head of planning) stated that:

"The work of some officials is hampered because of the lack of facilities in the office to support the work to be completed more quickly." And one of them is influenced by the lack of knowledge in carrying out each tupoksi and overlapping jobs, such as work that should be done by the head

of Kasie Kesra is done by the head of the government so that the work itself is neglected, as well as the lack of a sense of responsibility of each of our village officials."

The results of the interview show that in the implementation of tasks and by village officials there is still very little management due to the lack of ability. Sense of responsibility for tasks and also the lack of facilities and infrastructure at the bube village office is a separate obstacle from the apparatus so the output produced is very little and not on time in submitting reports from the results of their work.

Discipline

The results of interviews with each research informant can be found out that regarding the discipline of village officials through the implementation of performance appraisals of Bube village officials.

According to Mr. AH as the head of bube village with the question

"What is the level of discipline of the apparatus in carrying out tasks in the office?"

According to Mr. AH that:

"the discipline of the apparatus in carrying out tasks is considered ineffective due to the lack of a sense of responsibility for their work".

The same matter with the delivery of Mrs. MB as the mother (village secretary), she stated that:

"the discipline of the apparatus is less than the maximum in fulfilling the responsibilities of their work".

And according to Mrs. DK as (head of finance) that;

"the level of discipline of the apparatus needs to be improved both in the punctuality of entering and leaving work or completing work".

Furthermore, according to NB as (head of planning) that:

"It is necessary to evaluate performance every month in order to determine the best steps to maximize the level of discipline of village officials". (Interview October 2, 2021).

The results show that the discipline of the apparatus in carrying out their duties is assessed that employees must gain additional knowledge regarding the implementation of the obligations and responsibilities of each apparatus through technical guidance activities or capacity building training for village officials.

Leadership

Interviews conducted with informants regarding leadership were conducted to obtain information about the ability of a leader within the scope of village government to realize good governance.

According to Mr. AH the head of Bube Village with the question of how the leadership pattern is carried out in the Bube Village office environment, he explained:

"I as the village head fully entrust employees to carry out work by their responsibilities, as a leader I motivate village officials with a variety of strategies so that they are more enthusiastic in doing and completing their work, forms of motivation or strategies that I apply to them such as; giving compensation that is appropriate and balanced and making a good cooperation system, such as helping each other in completing work if the person concerned is sick or dealing and cannot be present at the office."

According to Mrs. MB (village secretary), she stated that:

"Overall, the village government is led by the village head, and as our leader, so far he has tried to run it well, and in the scope of administration I as the village secretary have the responsibility of carrying out and ensuring that village officials fulfill and comply with the policies and orders of the village head."

According to Mrs. DK (head of finance) that;

"The form of encouragement that is very often shown by superiors is to give appreciation or rewards to subordinates who prove more expertise, as a result, we subordinates can do a good job and feel happy with all the obligations they carry.

Next, for NB (head of planning), it's like this:

"For me, our Village Head is a democratic directive person whose ability to influence others to want to collaborate to achieve the goals that have been formalized with the method of various activities that will be tried to be determined together between the directive and subordinates and not only that, the village head also likes to provide assessments and bonuses at the end of the year for village officials who have completed their activity reports on time. Based on the conclusion of the interview above, it shows that in carrying out leadership tasks, the leadership of the Bube village head is seen to have tried to lead well, and as a leader he always motivates his subordinates and also likes to give assessments and bonuses at the end of the year to village officials who have completed activity reports on time.

Factors inhibiting the application of modern management to the performance of Bube village officials

1) Ability

The results of interviews conducted with informants with questions, namely:

"What is the level of expertise of Village officials in performing their obligations and functions?"

Bube Village Head AH, he explained that:

"Indeed, for the past few years, the quality of work or performance of the apparatus has not been maximized, not only because they are inexperienced, but they also have not received training or technical guidance on procedures or techniques in managing administration, both in the field of government administration and the field of development, but recently with the technical guidance on increasing the capacity of village officials, alhamdulillah now village officials are at least able to manage their respective activities, and especially the quality of performance is not good, because there are many shortcomings, especially in actions that always delay work, so that it is often late in the process of completion."

According to the MB Village Secretary that:

"As long as I have been the village secretary, I have understood, if there are also some things that we do not understand, we can ask the village facilitator, and regarding our abilities, alhamdulillah some of our officials are capable and have very good work quality, as evidenced by several documents that were completed and reported earlier than other villages in Suwawa sub-district."

Then the Head of Planning NB said that:

"If it is a question of aspects I have understood, but I am still constrained by my skills in operating Microsoft Office applications, and for that I am still often assisted and guided by our secretary."

The same question was answered by the Head of DK Finance, who explained that

"As for the ability of each village apparatus in working in the village government, for me it has been better than in previous years, at least for this year we have understood and understood each other's main tasks and functions, but the ability here will also mean nothing for a job, if it is not supported by a sense of responsibility and willingness to complete it, there are indeed several obstacles that we feel when trying to fulfill these responsibilities, for example right now we lack facilities in the form of computers, printers, work desks, and narrow workspaces."

He continued that:

From some of the statements above, the description skills, and expertise of some village officials are lacking, both in the orderly administration of the village and skills in using facilities such as computers. (Interview October 2, 2021).

2) Employee Discipline

By observations and interviews with the Head of Bube AH Village, and other informants with questions, namely:

"One form of assessing the performance of village officials that contains modern management principles is discipline, do village officials work with actions and obedient attitudes in the application of their obligations and responsibilities so far?",

he explained that:

"If judged in terms of discipline, the ability of the village apparatus is very lacking, starting from the success of office hours which should be 07.30 to 16:00 but the reality on activity days sometimes not open and sometimes not until 4 pm has closed, but if there is urgent work the village apparatus without having to be urged they will work overtime until the night and even come to work on Saturdays and Sundays, but for some village officials it is very far from the word discipline let alone being responsible for their duties and functions."

According to Mrs. MB (village secretary), she stated that:

"I still have difficulty in coordinating village officials, as a form of my responsibility to the village head, I can only tighten the schedule for completing work, especially reports on activities that have been carried out so that at the time of the inspection schedule by the inspectorate auditor all reports have been completed."

According to Mrs. DK as (head of finance) that;

"As a financial head who is responsible for paying, and making financial reports, I am very difficult to complete quickly, because it is constrained by the implementers of activities who are often not at the office on time, and some are absent from work."

Furthermore, according to NB as (head of planning) that:

"In carrying out the profession, sometimes we can complete the profession according to the duration, related to the submitted profession. sometimes there is a profession that wants a duration of 2 days or 3 days so it cannot be over in 1 day, sometimes there is through duration, related to the submitted profession "

The results of the interview above can conclude that the form of modern management in the management of the Bube village government has not been fully implemented by some village officials in the management of village government. This matter is seen in the statement of the village head, where the discipline and responsibility of village officials in carrying out their duties and functions are still lacking, thus affecting the value of the performance achievements of some village officials.

3) Cooperation

In interviews with informants, namely how cooperation between Bube village officials in carrying out and completing their duties and responsibilities, Mr. AH, he explained:

"Relationships between village officials must be established In carrying out work, sometimes we can handle work that takes a long time, adrift with the work submitted. often there is work that takes 2 days or 3 days so it cannot be completed in 1 day, often there is a long pass, adrift with the work submitted, it's just that some village officials who are not responsible for their work often come late, and some do not enter the office".

According to Mrs. MB (village secretary), she stated that:

"Until now, I have not only coordinated the activities and work of our officials, but also helped in their completion, because they have just attended technical guidance on the implementation of their respective duties and functions, so they are still in the process of learning both administratively and technically."

According to Mrs. DK (head of finance);

"As long as there is a duration of availability to help and our obligations have ended, even though it is not my obligation if it is needed, we are ready to help, but sometimes those who are helped are not located in the office."

According to NB (head of planning) that:

"Each officer has their duties and functions but other features may want our power and mind to be available to help".

The results of the question and answer above can be concluded that each Village officer has a different profession from one another, but Village officers can carry out good cooperation, but the aspect of managing abilities related to cooperation is, when the officer responsible for the work is not in the office on time, even absent from work so that this matter greatly affects the process of completing work.

5. Conclusion and Recommendation

Based on the research conducted in the matter of analyzing the ability of village officials based on modern management at the Bube Village Office, Suwawa District, Bone-Bolango Regency, the following conclusions can be drawn

1. The performance of village officials in the Bube village office has not been maximized because some village officials are not disciplined in terms of time, both in terms of attendance, as well as timeliness in completing tasks and responsibilities, but with the existence of a firm leadership spirit by the village head and guidance carried out by the village secretary in handling delays in the work of village officials, as well as cooperation carried out by several village officials in helping complete the work of other officials so that these jobs can be completed simultaneously. Improved performance of village officials is also influenced by several modern management principles related to performance evaluation conducted by the village head at the end of the month is a form of application of the government management function itself, where the goal is to obtain better results by making improvements and improving performance, thus the ability of village officials will increase.

2. Factors inhibiting the performance of village officials

a. Ability

The way of handling obligations by some Bube Village officers is less efficient and efficient, a kind of lack of energy base of people from the village apparatus so the aspect of expertise in handling the obligations and responsibilities of each village apparatus.

b. Employee Discipline

The form of modern management in the management of bube village government has not been fully implemented by some village officials in the management of village government. This matter is influenced by the discipline and responsibility of village officials in the implementation of their duties and functions which are still lacking, thus affecting the value of the performance achievements of some village officials.

c. Cooperation

Village officials are able to establish good cooperation, but what is a factor inhibiting performance related to cooperation is when the apparatus responsible for the work is not in the office on time, even absent from work so that this matter greatly affects the completion process.

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